

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

MOLECULAR DOCKING STUDIES OF N-(1-(BENZO[d]THIAZOL-2-YLAMINO)-2,2,2-TRICHLOROETHYL)-CARBOXAMIDES AS A_{2A} RECEPTOR POTENTIAL ANTAGONISTS.**Pavlo V. Zadorozhnii, Ihor O. Pokotylo, Vadym V. Kiselev, Aleksandr V. Kharchenko, Oxana V. Okhtina**

Department of Organic Substances and Pharmaceutical Preparations, Ukrainian State University of Chemical Technology, Gagarin Ave., 8, Dnipro 49005, Ukraine.

Absrtacts:

In this work, using the ArgusLab 4.0.1 software package, we carried out in silico modeling of A_{2A} receptor antagonists. We proposed N-(1-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)carboxamides as potential biologically active substances. According to the results of molecular docking, all of the analyzed benzo[d]thiazol-2-amine derivatives were superior to ZM-241385 in the strength of the complex formed with the receptor. N-(1-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)-4-methylbenzamide, N-(1-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)-1-naphthamide and N-(2,2,2-trichloro-1-((6-chlorobenzo[d]thiazol-2-yl)amino)ethyl)benzamide formed the most stable complexes with the A_{2A} receptor. For all studied structures, an acute toxicity prediction for rats was made using the GUSAR program. In addition, the compounds studied were tested for compliance with Lipinski criteria.

Keywords: *In silico, Molecular docking, A_{2A}, GUSAR, ArgusLab, Benzo[d]thiazol, Carboxamides.***Corresponding author:****Pavlo V. Zadorozhnii,**

Department of Organic Substances and Pharmaceutical Preparations,

Ukrainian State University of Chemical Technology,

Gagarin Ave., 8, Dnipro 49005, Ukraine.

E-mail: torfp@i.ua; Tel. +38(067)425-27-10, Fax: +38(0562)47-33-16.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Pavlo V. Zadorozhnii et al., *Molecular Docking Studies of N-(1-(Benzo[d]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)carboxamides as A_{2a} Receptor Potential Antagonists.*, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci.*, 2019; 06(01).

INTRODUCTION:

Adenosine receptors are widely represented in different types of tissues and are involved in the regulation of a number of biological processes, their common natural agonist being adenosine. Based on different selectivity to adenosine analogues, as well as on biochemical and pharmacological properties, adenosine receptors are divided into four subtypes (A_1 , A_{2A} , A_{2B} , and A_3) [1]. The A_{2A} receptor regulates myocardial oxygen consumption by expanding the coronary vessels [2], takes part in suppressing inflammatory processes and thereby protects tissues from damage [3]. In addition, this receptor is expressed in the brain, where it plays an important role in regulating the release of glutamate and dopamine [4]. Therefore, the A_{2A} receptor is a promising potential therapeutic target for the treatment of heart disease, inflammatory processes, insomnia, pain, depression, addiction, Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's disease and other neurodegenerative diseases, as well as asthma, rheumatoid arthritis, psoriasis [5].

Given the enormous potential of the A_{2A} receptor as a therapeutic target, the urgency of searching for its new antagonists is beyond doubt. Recently, an increasing number of studies have been devoted to the search and modeling of A_{2A} receptor antagonists [6]. Of particular interest in this quality are derivatives of benzimidazole [7], benzoxazole [8], and benzthiazole [9].

In this paper, we proposed *N*-(1-(benzo[*d*]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)carboxamides as potential A_{2A} receptor antagonists. Structures for research were taken from the open database of chemical compounds PubChem [10]. The search for compounds leaders was based on molecular docking results [11,12].

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

1. Molecular docking procedure:

We have carried out geometry optimization of analyzed structures within PM3 semi-empirical method, and A_{2A} molecular docking using software ArgusLab 4.0.1 [13]. Previously, this software package was successfully used to solve similar problems [14-19].

1.1 Protein preparation:

The three-dimensional crystal structure of co-crystallizer A_{2A} and ZM-241385 (PDB ID: 3EML) [20] has been loaded in PDB format from the data bank of protein molecules (<http://www.rcsb.org>). All crystallization inclusions (water molecules, stearic acid and sulfate ions), with the exception of 401 ZMA, were removed before molecular docking. Before the molecular docking, the hydrogen atoms

were added throughout the protein structure.

1.2 Ligand preparation:

On the basis of remaining inhibitor molecule (code in co-crystallizer 401 ZMA), we have created ligand group named Ligand_X-ray. A three-dimensional model of the binding site has been created on the basis of this group, its dimensions being calculated automatically and being along the X-axis - 18.506, Y-axis - 12.990 and the Z-axis - 21.844 Å. Docking has been done with a flexible ligand. A semi-empirical AScore function has been used to the scoring procedure, based on the XScore function [21]. The cell resolution has been set at 0.250 Å. The calculation type has been Dock; Docking Engine - ArgusLab. Visualization of the results has been carried out using program PyMOL [22].

2. Toxic prediction:

The prediction of acute toxicity for rats was performed using the GUSAR program [23]. We have introduced the structures of compounds for biological activity prediction using the graphical editor *Marvin Sketch* at the official website (<http://www.pharmaexpert.ru>). Then, these structures have been sent to the server as MNA-descriptors (*Multilevel Neighborhoods of Atoms*) [24,25]. The results of the prediction of biological activity spectrum have been visualized on the display and saved by "copy-paste".

3. Check for compliance with the rules of Lipinski:

Using the Molinspiration web resource (<http://www.molinspiration.com/cgi-bin/properties>), the compounds studied were tested for compliance with Lipinski criteria [26].

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

When performing molecular docking with the A_{2A} receptor as a reference, we used 4-(2-(7-amino-2-(furan-2-yl)-[1,2,4]triazolo[1,5-*a*][1,3,5]triazin-5-yl-amino)ethyl)phenol (ZM-241385) [27], the calculated binding energy with the active center of the enzyme being -9.53 kcal/mol, the calculation time being 4 s. The calculated results of ZM-241385 in the active site of the receptor differed slightly from the results obtained by X-ray analysis (Fig. 1), root-mean-square deviation of atomic positions being 2.1 Å. The position of the heterocyclic part of the antagonist almost coincided, and the main difference was associated with the conformation of the alkylaryl substituent. The system of intermolecular hydrogen bonds between the ZM-241385 molecule and the amino acids of the A_{2A} active center remained almost unchanged. Thus, according to X-ray structural analysis [20] (Fig. 1a), there were three intermolecular hydrogen bonds between the ZM-241385 molecule and the amino acids of the active

A_{2A} site. Two of them were formed with the participation of the amino group ZM-241385 and the side radicals Asn 253 and Gln 169 (3.0 Å and 3.4 Å in length, respectively). The third hydrogen bond was formed by the Oxygen atom of the furan cycle and the amide group Asn 253, the bond length $O...H_2NC(O)$ (Asn 253) being 3.3 Å. According to the calculated data (Fig. 1b), there were four

intermolecular hydrogen bonds between the ZM-241385 molecule and the amino acids of the active site A_{2A} , three of which (2.9 Å, 3.5 Å and 3.2 Å in length) were formed with the participation of the amide group Asn 253, and one - with the participation of the residue of the carboxyl group Leu 267 (2.8 Å in length).

Fig. 1: The position of the ZM-241385 molecule in the active site of A_{2A} receptor, according to X-ray diffraction analysis (a) [20] and molecular docking (b), the energy of the complex is -9.53 kcal/mol. RMSD is 2.1 Å. Visualization in PyMOL [22].

According to the results of molecular docking, all of the analyzed benzo[*d*]thiazol-2-amine derivatives were superior to ZM-241385 in the strength of the complex formed with the receptor. *N*-(1-(benzo[*d*]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)-4-methylbenzamide (7), *N*-(1-(benzo[*d*]thiazol-2-

ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)-1-naphthamide (9) and *N*-(2,2,2-trichloro-1-((6-chlorobenzo[*d*]thiazol-2-yl)amino)ethyl)benzamide (16) formed the most stable complexes with A_{2A} . The energy of the complexes with other studied structures was somewhat higher (Table 1).

Table 1: The result of molecular docking of *N*-(1-(benzo[*d*]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)carboxamides with A_{2A} .

Comp.	R	X	PubChem ID	Name	ΔG , kcal/mol
1	CH ₃	H	18879601	<i>N</i> -(1-(benzo[<i>d</i>]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)acetamide	-9.79
2	CH ₂ Cl	H	18879599	<i>N</i> -(1-(benzo[<i>d</i>]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)-2-chloroacetamide	-9.63
3	CH ₂ CH(CH ₃)CH ₃	H	18879600	<i>N</i> -(1-(benzo[<i>d</i>]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)-3-methylbutanamide	-10.47
4	C ₆ H ₅	H	18879595	<i>N</i> -(1-(benzo[<i>d</i>]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)benzamide	-11.16
5	2-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	H	18879596	<i>N</i> -(1-(benzo[<i>d</i>]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)-2-methylbenzamide	-12.07
6	3-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	H	18879597	<i>N</i> -(1-(benzo[<i>d</i>]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)-3-methylbenzamide	-12.08
7	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	H	18879598	<i>N</i> -(1-(benzo[<i>d</i>]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)-4-methylbenzamide	-12.36
8	4-FC ₆ H ₄	H	3829997	<i>N</i> -(1-(benzo[<i>d</i>]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)-4-fluorobenzamide	-11.67
9	α -Naphthyl	H	18879602	<i>N</i> -(1-(benzo[<i>d</i>]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)-1-naphthamide	-13.75
10	Thien-2-yl	H	4577801	<i>N</i> -(1-(benzo[<i>d</i>]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)thiophene-2-carbox-amide	-11.43
11	CH ₃	CH ₃	4624289	<i>N</i> -(2,2,2-trichloro-1-((6-methylbenzo[<i>d</i>]thiazol-2-yl)amino)ethyl)acetamide	-10.49
12	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	5171080	<i>N</i> -(2,2,2-trichloro-1-((6-methylbenzo[<i>d</i>]thiazol-2-yl)amino)ethyl)benzamide	-11.75
13	CH ₃	Br	4670533	<i>N</i> -(1-((6-bromobenzo[<i>d</i>]thiazol-2-yl)amino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)acetamide	-10.25
14	CH ₂ Cl	SCN	5011422	2-chloro- <i>N</i> -(2,2,2-trichloro-1-((6-thiocyanatobenzo[<i>d</i>]thiazol-2-yl)amino)ethyl)acetamide	-10.69
15	C ₆ H ₅	SCN	331996	<i>N</i> -(2,2,2-trichloro-1-((6-thiocyanatobenzo[<i>d</i>]thiazol-2-yl)amino)ethyl)benzamide	-11.63
16	C ₆ H ₅	Cl	5155175	<i>N</i> -(2,2,2-trichloro-1-((6-chlorobenzo[<i>d</i>]thiazol-2-yl)amino)ethyl)benzamide	-12.23
17	C ₆ H ₅	NO ₂	3477480	<i>N</i> -(2,2,2-trichloro-1-((6-nitrobenzo[<i>d</i>]thiazol-2-yl)amino)ethyl)benzamide	-10.36

N-(1-(Benzo[*d*]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)-4-methylbenzamide (**7**), *N*-(1-(benzo[*d*]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)-1-naphthamide (**9**) and *N*-(2,2,2-trichloro-1-((6-chlorobenzo[*d*]thiazol-2-yl)amino)ethyl)benzamide (**16**) effectively bound to the active site of the

receptor (Fig. 2). Compound (**16**) was additionally stabilized in the receptor active center (Fig. 2c) through the formation of an intermolecular hydrogen bond between the Oxygen atom of the amide group and the amide group Asn 253, the C=O...H₂NC(O) (Asn 253) bond being 3.5 Å in length.

Fig. 2: The position of the *N*-(1-(benzo[*d*]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)carboxamides molecule in the active site of A_{2A} receptor, according to molecular docking: a) *N*-(1-(benzo[*d*]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)-1-naphthamide (**9**) the energy of the complex is -13.75 kcal/mol; b) *N*-(1-(benzo[*d*]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)-4-methylbenzamide (**7**) the energy of the complex is -12.36 kcal/mol; c) *N*-(2,2,2-trichloro-1-((6-chlorobenzo[*d*]thiazol-2-yl)amino)ethyl)benzamide (**16**) the energy of the complex is -12.23 kcal/mol. Visualization in PyMOL [22].

All analyzed structures meet Lipinski criteria, and their calculated toxicity is significantly lower than that of ZM-241385 (Table 2).

Table 2: The results of testing *N*-(1-(benzo[*d*]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)carboxamides for compliance with Lipinski criteria and their acute toxicity forecast results.

Comp.	Mr	logP	Rot.Bond	H _{donor}	H _{acceptor}	Toxic LD ₅₀ (mg/kg)	
						IV*	Oral**
1	338.65	3.32	4	2	4	125.30	1466.00
2	373.09	3.89	5	2	4	106.80	643.40
3	380.73	4.93	6	2	4	7704	732.40
4	400.72	4.99	5	2	4	189.20	1625.00
5	414.75	5.39	5	2	4	147.30	1658.00
6	414.75	5.42	5	2	4	140.30	2173.00
7	414.75	5.44	5	2	4	141.40	1696.00
8	418.71	5.16	5	2	4	230.70	1337.00
9	450.78	6.15	5	2	4	185.80	2427.00
10	406.75	4.89	5	2	4	195.40	1302.00
11	352.67	3.75	4	2	4	85.10	1512.00
12	414.75	5.42	5	2	4	149.90	1626.00
13	417.54	4.11	4	2	4	222.50	2572.00
14	430.17	4.07	6	2	5	149.20	1618.00
15	457.80	5.18	6	2	5	293.90	1575.00
16	435.16	5.65	5	2	4	220.90	1551.00
17	445.71	4.93	6	2	7	231.50	1159.00
ZM-241385	337.34	2.12	5	4	9	41.88	1040.00

* IV - The estimated LD₅₀ value in intravenous administration.

** Oral - The estimated LD₅₀ value in oral administration.

CONCLUSION:

In this paper, we conducted *in silico* modeling of the A_{2A} receptor antagonists. *N*-(1-(benzo[*d*]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl) carboxamides were suggested as potential biologically active substances. According to the results of molecular docking, all analytes are superior to ZM-241385 in the strength of the complex formed with the receptor. The most stable complexes with the A_{2A} receptor form *N*-(1-(benzo[*d*]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)-4-methylbenzamide, *N*-(1-(benzo[*d*]thiazol-2-ylamino)-2,2,2-trichloroethyl)-1-naphthamide and *N*-(2,2,2-trichloro-1-((6-chlorobenzo[*d*]thiazol-2-yl)amino)-ethyl)benzamide. All analyzed structures meet Lipinski criteria, and their calculated toxicity is significantly lower than that of ZM-241385. The compounds hits can be recommended for further study *in vitro* and *in vivo*.

REFERENCES:

- Piirainen H, Ashok Y, Nanekar RT, Jaakola V-P. Structural features of adenosine receptors: From crystal to function. *Biochim Biophys Acta*, 2011; 1808 (5): 1233-1244.
- Headrick JP, Peart JN, Reichelt ME, Haseler LJ. Adenosine and its receptors in the heart: Regulation, retaliation and adaptation. *Biochim Biophys Acta*, 2011; 1808 (5): 1413-1428.
- Palmer TM, Trevethick MA. Suppression of inflammatory and immune responses by the A_{2A} adenosine receptor: an introduction. *British J Pharmacol*, 2008; 153 (Suppl 1): S27-S34.
- Franco R, Navarro G. Adenosine A_{2A} Receptor Antagonists in neurodegenerative Diseases: Huge potential and Huge Challenges. *Front Psychiatry*, 2018; 9: 68.
- Ruiz ML, Lim Y-H, Zheng J. Adenosine A_{2A} Receptor as a Drug Discovery Target. *J Med Chem*, 2014; 57 (9): 3623-3650.
- Jazayeri A, Andrews SP, Marshall FH. Structurally Enabled Discovery of Adenosine A_{2A} Receptor Antagonists. *Chem Rev*, 2017; 117 (1): 21-37.
- Ghatol SP, Verma S, Agarwal K, Sharon A. Pharmacophore Distance Mapping and Docking Study of Some Benzimidazole Analogs as A_{2A} Receptor Antagonists. *Int J Pharm Sci Drug Res*, 2010; 2(1): 71-77.
- Duroux R, Renault N, Cuelho JE, Agouridas L, Blum D, Lopes LV, Melnyk P, Yous S. Design, synthesis and evaluation of 2-aryl benzoxazoles as promising hit for the A_{2A} receptor. *J Enzyme Inhib Med Chem*, 2017; 32 (1): 850-864.
- Yuan G, Jankins TC, Patrick CG Jr, Philbrook P,

- Sears O, Hatfield S, Sitkovsky M, Vasdev N, Liang SH, Ondrechen MJ, Pollastri MP, Jones GB. Fluorinated Adenosine A_{2A} Receptor Antagonists Inspired by Preladenant as Potential Cancer Immunotherapeutics. *Int J Med Chem*, 2017; 2017: 4852537.
10. Wang Y, Bryant SH, Cheng T, Wang J, Gindulyte A, Shoemaker BA, Thiessen PA, He S, Zhang J. PubChem BioAssay: 2017 update. *Nucleic Acids Res*, 2017; 45 (D1): D955-D963.
 11. Young DC. 2009. Computational drug design. New Jersey, USA: John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Hoboken.
 12. Holtje H-D, Sippl W, Rognan D, Folkers R. 2008. Molecular Modeling. Basic Principles and Applications. Weinheim, Germany: Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA.
 13. Thompson M. ArgusLab 4.0.1. Planaria software LLC, Seattle, Wash, USA, 2004. <http://www.arguslab.com>
 14. Varmaan V, Rani Y, Avupati VR. *In silico* based virtual screening for bioactive PPAR- γ agonists. *Indo Amer J Pharm Sci*, 2016; 3 (10): 1237-1250.
 15. James T, Rajendran A, Martin Sh, Easo R, Krishnan NC, Manakadan AA, Saranya TS. Computational Approach on The Drug Affinity Studies of Substituted (4-Aminophenyl)Benzothiazole Derivatives Against Colon Cancer. *Res J Pharm, Biol Chem Sci*, 2017; 8 (2): 402-407.
 16. Reddy YS, Girdhar M, Mohan A, Mohan V, Sharma NR. Bioinformatics Based Study on Curcumin Pharmacophore and its Suitability as Natural Remedy for Diabetes. *Res J Pharm, Biol Chem Sci*, 2015; 6 (1): 1088-1096.
 17. Thong ChT, Avupati VR. Synthesis, *in vitro* biological evaluation and *in silico* molecular docking studies of some novel dihydropyrimidones as potential cytotoxic agents. *Indo Amer J Pharm Sci*, 2016; 3 (10): 1251-1263.
 18. Zadorozhnii PV, Kiselev VV, Titova AE, Kharchenko AV, Pokotylo IO, Okhtina OV. Molecular Docking Studies of *N*-5-Aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazolo-2,2-dichloroacetamidines as Inhibitors of Enoyl-ACP Reductase *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *Res J Pharm Technol*, 2017; 10(4): 1091-1097.
 19. Zadorozhnii PV, Kiselev VV, Teslenko NO, Kharchenko AV, Pokotylo IO, Okhtina OV, Kryshchuk OV. *In Silico* Prediction and Molecular Docking Studies of *N*-Amidoalkylated Derivatives of 1,3,4-Oxadiazole as COX-1 and COX-2 Potential Inhibitors. *Res J Pharm Technol*, 2017; 10(11): 3957-3963.
 20. Jaakola VP, Griffith MT, Hanson MA, Cherezov V, Chien EY, Lane JR, Ijzerman AP, Stevens RC. The 2.6 angstrom crystal structure of a human A_{2A} adenosine receptor bound to an antagonist. *Science*, 2008; 322 (5905): 1211-1217.
 21. Wang R, Lai L, Wang S. Further development and validation of empirical scoring functions for structure-based binding affinity prediction. *J Comput Aided Mol Des*, 2002; 16(1): 11-26.
 22. DeLano WL. The PyMOL Molecular Graphics System, DeLano Scientific: Palo Alto, CA, 2003. (<http://www.pymol.org>)
 23. Lagunin A, Zakharov A, Filimonov D, Poroikov V. QSAR modelling of rat acute toxicity on the basis of PASS prediction. *Mol Inf*, 2011; 30 (2-3): 241-250.
 24. Filimonov DA, Lagunin AA, Glorizova TA, Rudik AV, Druzhilovskii DS, Pogodin PV, Poroikov VV. Prediction of the biological activity spectra of organic compounds using the PASS online web resource. *Chem Heterocycl Comp*, 2014; 50 (3): 444-457.
 25. Sadyr AV, Lagunin AA, Filimonov DA, Poroikov VV. Internet System Predicting the Spectrum of Biological Activity of Chemical Compounds. *Pharmaceut Chem J*, 2002; 36 (10): 538-543.
 26. Lipinski CA, Lombardo F, Dominy BW, Feeney PJ. Experimental and computational approaches to estimate solubility and permeability in drug discovery and development settings. *Adv Drug Delivery Rev*, 1997; 23 (1-3), 3-26.
 27. Jörg M, Agostino M, Yuriev E, Mak FS, Miller ND, White JM, Scammells PJ, Capuano B. Synthesis, molecular structure, NMR spectroscopic and computational analysis of a selective adenosine A_{2A} antagonist, ZM 241385. *Struct Chem*, 2013; 24 (4): 1241-1251.